

A Comparative Study of the Culture and Oral Literature of the Snake Charmers of the South and Eastern India

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Abstract: Here in this paper I want to show the relevance of the magic belief of the snake charmers of the Gangetic West Bengal and the southern states of India. Irulas, a tribal community of Tamil Nadu, Chengalpet region is mainly snake hunters. In Bengal these people belong to a specific tribe called 'BEDE' and they are doing this work from ancient time. These tribes are mainly wanderers. In South Asian countries we can find them in India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Malaysia etc. In North African countries of Egypt, Morocco and Tunisia this tradition is also practiced. On the other hand there are other specialized snake charmers in India who are not snake hunters.

As the south Bengal regions of India and Bangladesh both being river oriented wet lands, people here are worried about snake bite during the summer and monsoon seasons. Here the 'BEDE' communities catch the snakes and extract poison from the poisonous snake during and after rainy seasons from the paddy fields. They hunt the snakes and rats, sell the snake-poison, skins of the reptiles; and also sometimes earn by showing various acrobatics and folk dances . . .

The charmers not only charms the poisonous snakes, remove the reptile's fangs or venom glands or even sew the snake's mouth to shut it, but they often produce medicines from the snake poison. They also believe in malevolence effect in case they fail to satisfy their goddess Manasā. To please

Devi they use charms, sing songs and carry out dance performances in their village localities where they worship their deity.

The Irulas are similar to the Saperas so far their association with wild snakes is concerned, but they do not engage in snake charming, instead they practice hunting and export of snake skins. Their eco-sustainability is now disrupted and their community is near extinction. These communities are marginal, nomadic and are criminally suspected.

Key words: Benevolent and malevolent charm, rituals, performance, struggle of life.

Introduction:

India is always known as the land of exotic and intriguing cultures and traditions. But many of these cultures or the tribes and communities associated with them, have nearly disappeared in the face of the rapid urbanisation, and only a few that have managed to adapt still survive. The Irulas from Tamil Nadu are the skilled snake catchers of India. I have collected the data about them from Wikipedia and different internet source. Like them there are several tribal communities in India, found in every state, who are snake and rat hunters and spend their life by showing acrobatics on the street, selling snake skin, snake poison and hunting snakes to save the locality from snake bite.. On the other hand I am trying to project the actual position of Ojhās and Gunins, who are snake charmers and who know magical charms, rituals which are supposed to cure patients suffering from snake-bite and many other diseases. We can find Gunins all over India.

Irulas: While most of us tuck tail and run away at the very sight of a poisonous snake, catching venomous reptiles is a part of the daily life for the Irulas. Taking their name from the dark colour of their skin (*irular* means ‘the dark people’), the tribe historically survives by hunting reptiles, primarily snakes and rats which are menace to farmers in various parts of the state. However, the spread of modernism and the advent of new and improved methods for dealing with these problems in recent decades almost destroyed their livelihood. The population of snakes has dwindled over decades for various reasons.. Moreover the livelihood of the Irulas was nearly decimated overnight in 1972 when the Government of [India](#) banned the hunting and selling of snake skins- the chief source of income for the tribe.

However in recent years a considerable reversal of fortunes for the Irulas have been marked, Their natural expertise on how to deal with snakes and reptiles is now in demand at home and abroad.

Catching snakes and rodents through generations has equipped the Irulas with an expert understanding about these creatures. Their knowledge about the snakes often baffles even seasoned modern experts. Communities of Irulas in and around Chennai and Chengalpet have successfully transitioned to hunting snakes in urban and suburban areas, and some individuals of the community have even been found to acquire global acclaim. In 2017, two members of the Irula tribe, [Masi Sadaiyan and Vadivel Gopal](#), were commissioned to work in the USA, tasked with capturing Burmese pythons (an invasive species) in the Key Largo region in the Florida Keys. Accompanied by detection dogs, Sadaiyan and Gopal managed to capture an impressive 27 pythons in total. For their work, they were paid a sum of \$70,000. The expertise of the Irulas has since been in high demand all over the world.

The vocation of the Irulas takes the term ‘occupational hazards’ to a whole new level. While catching poisonous snakes and reptiles is a deadly activity, in any case the Irulas use a traditional method known as earthen pot fumigation, in which they blow smoke out of their mouths to weed out rodents. This method poses a serious health hazard and often leads to respiratory problems. Over the years, however, usage of the method has gone down significantly due to increased awareness.

After decades of near obscurity, the lives of the Irulas have improved immensely over the recent years, especially in regions around [Chennai](#). This is, in a large part, due to the efforts of several notable social workers, such as renowned herpetologist Romulus Whitaker of the [Madras Crocodile Bank Trust](#). Whitaker has worked towards providing income security for the Irulas for more than four decades. Today, most members of the Irula community near Chennai work as part of the Irula Snake-Catchers Cooperative, an organisation that uses their skills to capture poisonous snakes for the purpose of creating anti-venoms. Their new employment has worked well for them, and prices for catching poisonous snakes now range from Rs 500 to Rs 2,500 (for the king cobra). Furthermore, there has also been a tremendous improvement in the treatment of snake bites in and around Chennai, thanks to the availability of sufficient anti-venom.

While the Irulas have been successful in adapting to the modern world, they undoubtedly remain one of the very few communities that have preserved their ancient knowledge and traditions. This certainly makes them one of the most interesting tribes in the world.

Now I want to place some evidences of the ancient cultural practice of snake charming and snake worshipping in various parts of South India. A team of historians found an ancient inscription tablet along with a snake sculpture belonging to the 17th or 18th century on paleographic grounds close to the remote village of Pappappatti near Musiri. Several boulders of various sizes surrounded by thick vegetation can be seen in the outskirts of the village on the banks of a seasonal stream, locally called Panchamuga river. A team of historians, including Dr R Akila, assistant professor, Department of History along with Dr M Nalini, Head, Department of History, Seethalakshmi Ramaswami College visited the village and explored the entire area. The team found three engravings - two on slabs and one on a larger rock. Dr R Kalaikkovan, Director, Dr M Rajamanikkanar Centre for Historical Research, said, "One of the two slabs has a depiction of a crawling hooded cobra. The second slab has a well-sculpted pair of intertwined snakes. The two circles formed by their coils are used by the sculptor to exhibit a Linga and flower medallion. The Linga with a square base adorned with a garland occupies the top circle. The medallion is sculpted as a fully blossomed flower filling the lower circle.

Strong engraving and sculptures found near Musiri in Tiruchy. (Photo/ EPS)

The inscription engraved on the slab gives the name of an individual as Ayyannan, probably the donor."He added the larger rock which had a pair of footprints portrayed on one side is chiselled to make for a smooth surface on the lower side for the Tamil inscription. The 14 lines record the construction of a stone pavilion on the rocky path that lead to the temple of Venkatesvara Swami at Thalaimalai by Ayyannan, son of Venkatapathi, on the 14th of the Tamil month Thai in the year Vilambi. It mentions the name of the place where the inscription is found as Pandavanam and adds Ayyannan is always at the service of the Lord of Thalaimalai. It is also mentioned those who protect

the stone pavilion and the inscription would be blessed by the God of Thalaimalai with plenty of children. Thalaimalai is 3 km way from where the discovery was made and temple is presently known as Sanjiviraya Perumal Koyil. The presiding deity is Venkatachalapathy and the goddess is Alarmelmangai Thayar. [Source: <https://www.newindianexpress.com/states/tamil-nadu/2019/Dec/16/17th-century-inscription-snake-sculpture-found-in-tamil-nadu-2076819.html>]It is expected that the snake charmers were present in these areas and now also we can find them out easily.

Here I am showing you more evidences, collected from internet source, of the snake charmers of various provinces of South India. Snake gods and goddesses at various villages are worshipped till now and the Naga God is worshipped in temples, as per various stone inscriptions found from different states of India. The culture of snake charming and worshipping is an ancient culture and ritual of India.

Putru Amman Kovil, devine snakes living in termite hills. <http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

Putru Amman Kovil (temple). <http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

Putru Amman Kovil. <http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

Snake goddess Monchamma. Putru Amman, roadside snake worship.

<http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

Putru Amman snake shrine near Mamallapuram. <http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

Snake shrine on Thiruvakkarai Vakkrali Temple compound.

<http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

JHAM

Thiruvakkarai Vakkrali Temple. <http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

Thiruvakkarai Vakkrali Temple. <http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

Thiruvakkarai Vakkrakali Temple. <http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

In a Kali temple near Salem. <http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

Snake worship near Kanchipuram. <http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

Saptamatrika Goddesses the Seven Divine Mothers protected by snakes.
<http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

At Ayyanar temple near Anaikarai.

<http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

Naga stones. Bull Temple, Bangalore, Tamil Nadu.

<http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

Naga stones. Bull Temple, Bangalore, Tamil Nadu.

<http://www.blurb.com/books/3782738>

Two snakes facing each other over a Shiva-lingam on a pillar in Ulagamman temple at Tenkasi, Tamil Nadu. <http://www.blurb.com/bo>

From the record of the collections of the old photographs and paintings also we can find some example of the snake charmers who usually practice their charming skill and show in every village and town of the country.

From the Wikipedia https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snake_ charming
I have collected some examples.

Snakes have long been popular subjects of Hindu art, [Nāga](#), c. 1640, ([miniature](#))

[Daniel Hernández Morillo](#) *La charmeuse de serpents*, 1881

[Étienne Dinet](#), *The snake charmer*, 1889

Serpent Charmers

Indischer_Maler_um_1640_001 [Antonio Fabres](#), *The Young Snake Charmer*

Snake charmer of Jaipur

Snake charmer of Varanasi

JHAM

The Festival of the Snake charmers, Jhāmpān:

Most of the literatures on festivals underestimate a fundamental concept: the emphasis on social competition and contrasts. From the very definition of the festival, we lack an understanding of how the public display the festivities (parades, cultural performances, religious gatherings etc), emphasise social divisions which can be read as mirrors of conflicting social classes, values and worldviews. In particular, rites of public display (Falassi 1987) embedded within religious contexts explicitly exhibit social classes, their different roles, rankings, and underlying tensions.

The Jhāmpān is celebrated in West Bengal and Bangladesh in mid-August, during the day of worship of the snake-goddess Manasā. It is typically a gathering of Bede/Bediya/ Sapuṛe tribes and very few of Ojhās and takes shape as a procession: the Ojhā masters, surrounded by their disciples and accompanied by drums and devotional songs, display their skill in handling poisonous snakes, while the villagers enjoy the performance and follow the parade. Emerging from both literary survey and ethnographic field-work, the history of the decline of the performance of the Jhāmpān festival mirrors the crisis of the transmission of the Ojhā's knowledge, a crisis that can only be understood by considering the intersections between healing, ritual and entertainment.

In West Bengal the *Jhāmpān melā* or *parab* is very famous festival of the Bede/Bediya/ Sapuṛe tribes. They call it as 'Jhāmpān' or 'Lāvān' means to jump on. They appear at the festival field or *melā ground* by '*Chaturdolā*' or palanquin. There are 4-5 Jhāmpānī or to say Bediya/ Sapuṛe/, Ojhā, Gunin, Jāngurus etc. are usually come together. The snake cases or *Jhapias* are kept displayed side by side. The swings in the open field or fair are usually covered with a *Chandoā* or a decorated cloth hanged by binding the four sides. The fair field is usually decorated with colourful flags. The festival is held on the last day of the *shrāban* -the Bengali month of rainy season. This day is the day of Manasā or *mākhāl din*. At Bishnupur the day after *shrāban sankranti* is called *mākhāl parab*. This fair or festival is also held at Kochbihar, Rangpur and Jalpaiguri of North Bengal. All types of people irrespective of religion caste and creed celebrate and enjoy in this fair. One dead Bakul tree is the symbol of snake goddess of the shepherds. In Lalbagh, Beldanga of Murshidabad; Shearpur, Balāgarh, Magrā of Hoogli district; Nandigram, Balāi, Pāndāhāt of Midnapur; Cāltāberīā, Narar Ukharā, Durgāpur, Shāsan, Baruipur, Dhosar Hāt of 24 Parganas this *Jhāmpān Parab* is very famous. All the snake charmers, Sāpuṛes celebrate the day with procession, swinging Jhāmpis full of poisonous snakes and prove their worth before their Ostāds or Gurus. Some of them show acrobatics. For them the stage is fixed on two bamboos and it is called 'māchān' or 'Jhāmpān'. Sitting upon that raised seat like a horse rider the Ojhā/ Gunin or Sāpuṛes show their collection of snakes and play with them. The word 'Jhāmpān' has another application, that it is a special type of charm which is applied to cure the snake-bite patients at their last stage of medication. In this 'Jhāmpān' festival we can find out few women Gunins also who show their power of snake charming from the high platform. Then the Sāpuṛes dance with the cluster of snakes holding them all over their body. They showcase the snakes and play with them. They sing the prayer song of Manasā by praising her and with that they play Bīn, and other instruments. They also dance and play various acrobatics and enjoy various jokes and funs. The Sāpuṛes wear *ghumur* or copper bells in their wrists and anklet and act the play of Manasāmangal

Pālā and sing and dance with various poison healing charms like *bāṅmārā*, *bāṅkātā*, *Jhāmpān*, *netānī*, *tāgā*, *tagbandhan*, *tāgākātan*, *bish urān*, *chāpān-utor* etc. There they enjoy selling facilities of different types of herbs, amulets, rings, poisonous stone for wearing purpose. After worshipping their Goddess they offer milk and banana with other fruits as *naibedyā* to their snakes. After all these rituals the villagers take their *prasād* or food offered to the goddess. The women celebrate another vow of making friends ‘Saylā’ just after this festival. This vow has separate songs as friendship song or *sai pātānor gān*.¹

Jhāmpān as enactment of folk healer’s Social drama

Other groups of specialised practitioners dealing with snake-bites are colloquially called by Bengali outsiders as *sāpuṛe* (*sāp* means snake). They are members of a social group named Bede or Bedia², traditionally a nomadic tribe, now mostly settled in rural West Bengal (Dash 2011: 20), where there are possibly 100.000 members of this community (ibid.). Although many Bede households at present derive their income from daily agricultural labour, especially during rice harvesting and planting³, their traditional activities are centred on snakes and performances. Bedes are exceptionally skilled snake-catchers whom the terrified households would call and rely upon in order to get rid of poisonous snakes that infest Bengali villages during summer and monsoon seasons. Members of this group would daily go about in the countryside with a stick, a dagger and a piece of *sarpagandhā*, a wood whose smell can keep the snakes at a distance, and look for snakes. They possess sophisticated knowledge in recognizing and handling snakes, which they keep in covered baskets smeared with cow-dung. Snake catching and snake charming are major means of livelihood of the Bedes'. Poisonous snakes are 'milked' once a month and the poison is sold to private doctors and chemical laboratories for the production of anti-venom serum.⁴ Beautiful and impressive snakes are used for public performances of snake-charming⁵, often accompanied by drums and the typical wind instrument called *bīṅ*, or sold to other members of the community for their performances. In the festive season when *Manasā* is worshipped, troupes of Bedes travel to different villages to offer their skills as musicians and singers of *Manasā* songs, which they perform while displaying and 'charming' their snakes. Although the community defines itself as Muslim, their religious status is highly ambiguous. As worshippers of *Manasā* they are not formally recognized as Muslims by the orthodoxy, while at the same time, since they follow Muslim customs and rites of passage, they are excluded from the Hindu establishment. Their healing techniques are based on the preparation of herbal and plant-based medicines, although they also give consecrated amulets (*tabij*) for protection against illness and evil eye, in exchange of money or rice. While the term Bede or Bedia is of uncertain origins (possibly linked to the Vaidya caste

of doctor's profession), Bede snake-catchers and snake-charmers consider their original ancestor and the progenitor of their group to be the Kamru Guru (Dash 2011: 61). Some of them believe that the name derives from bedouin since the tribe originally came from the Middle East. The recent emphasis on the monogenesis of so-called gypsies helped in reshaping and ennobling the definition of the Bedias of Bangladesh, who normally live on boats, as "river gypsies" (e.g. Suhrawardi 2015:53). The Bedes of West Bengal suffer from a huge amount of legal marginality and vulnerability: their literacy rate being close to 1% (Dash: 2011: 19) and their ambiguous religious status being impossible to record on a census, the Bedes are not given a voter identity card nor a ration card (**to verify**), and remain invisible to mainstream society. Together with the legal restriction on capturing or killing wild life, their position in the Bengali society has become utterly fragile since their activities were made illegal by specific governmental policies. The Wildlife Protection Act of 1972⁶ declared that capturing and keeping wild animals is punishable by law. The 2002 amendment of the same law made its enforcement even stricter. Snake-catchers and snake-charmers found themselves guilty for carrying out their traditional occupations which is now severely punishable with sanctions and jail sentences. At the same time, in the rural world their profession is still extremely functional and unavoidable. About fifty thousand people die of snake-bite in India every year (Cook and Zumla 2009:561). Poison is needed in order to produce the highly valuable antidote that is still so scarcely available at local clinics and hospitals. Traditional remedies for first aid and treatment of snake-bites are absolutely necessary, especially in remote areas where hospitals are hardly reachable. Rural snake specialists thus remain trapped in the contradictions and the hypocrisy that mediate transitions between "the State and the village". Local animalists threaten the practitioners with verbal as well as concrete actions: many Bedes reported that they have been forced several times by an animal rights activist to get rid of all the snakes that they had collected and free them in the jungle; otherwise they would be imprisoned at the closest police station. The Kolkata-based socialist company(?) of street theatre "of the oppressed" Jana Sanskriti⁷ toured rural villages to discourage people to rely upon traditional healers (Ojhās and Guṇins) through their awareness campaigns, the indigenous knowledge is discredited as mere superstition that is rooted only where modern medical structures and biomedical facilities did not reach. A famous line of their play says "snakes live in the village: the antidotes live in the city". As Da Costa suggested, while the "theatre of the oppressed" emphasized an unequal system of rural healthcare, their statements also misrecognized a long history of indigenous health practices and role of goddesses of health in people's lives, posing the access to modern healthcare in a mutually exclusive relation to the lived religion and healing practices (Da Costa 2013: VII). This neglected the fact that Ojhās and Bedes usually earn 150-250 Rupees per

day as agricultural labourer. Snake-catchers would generally receive about 700 Rupees for selling the poison extracted from one snake. Other performativity and artistic activities transmitted among the Bede groups are: magic tricks, juggling, acrobatics, tattoo making, scroll-painting and storytelling, disguising with colourful masks and costumes (bahurūpī) etc. Several communities whose survival is connected with the taming and using of wild animals have been jeopardized due to the enforcement of this law. About the impact of the Wildlife Preservation Act on the itinerant performer groups Hawadiga and Qalandar in Karnataka writings of Ajit Kumar (2012-13) may be seen.. Villagers often have coexisting complex beliefs in 'modern' medicine and 'traditional' healing while practitioners of traditional system end up being relegated to an even more “oppressed” status. Several consequences derived from the severe enforcement of the Wildlife Preservation Act. The snake catchers constantly live in the fear of being arrested. They travel by cheap local buses, which are often their only option, hiding their baskets full of snakes which become extremely risky sometimes. Repeated performances of snake-charming become dangerous. Remuneration is also very little, since modern audiences lack interest in such performances and enjoy more glamorous entertainments dictated by the rules of the TV and the film industries. Selling poison illegally to private clinics and pharmaceutical laboratories is subjected to the rules of the black market. Thus snake-catchers often have no say in the negotiations of selling price and are compelled to agree to whatever price is offered by the buyer – who will then sell the snake venom in its dry crystallised form between \$1,000 to \$1,500 per gram on the international market. The superimposed circumstances (?) suggested a viable solution for the snake-catchers of West Bengal, i.e smuggling wild snakes through the border with Bangladesh, where Wildlife Protection Act as promulgated internationally is not so strongly enforced. The black market of snakes from India to Bangladesh constitutes the primary source for the international mafia that manages the worldwide traffic of snakes and snake-derived products (mainly skin and venom for research purposes). The main centres of this black market in Bangladesh is in Dhaka and Pabna (Dash 2011: 52-53). An additional problematic aspect highlighted and mater of concern is the collection of wild plants used for the preparation of traditional medicines. Governmental subsidies have encouraged extensive agriculture in West Bengal: following the emphasis towards “cash crop cultivation”. Local landowners are interested in possessing an increasing quantity of cleared land to cultivate agricultural produces. Thus large portions of forest have been cleared for building new roads and for agricultural purposes, therefore a number of shrubs were extirpated in order to prepare the soil for cultivation. Ojhās and local healers, who mainly use wild plants, roots and saps for preparation of their remedies, are witnessing an increasing difficulty in finding out the plants needed for medical goals.⁸ At the same

time, health-care assistance centres managed by the Government as well as by NGOs offer consultancy and medicament free of charge for destitute rural families, encouraging them to distrust folk healers. Consequently, only the most marginalized, poor and uneducated members of the village are left to seek help from local practitioners – such as Ojhās, Dāi midwives, Kabirāji herbalists, Fakir healers etc who are left with a meagre income and a declining social power.⁹

Ojhā and Gunin: The name Ojhā, supposedly derived from the corruption of the Sanskrit term upādhyāya, is diffused within and beyond Bengal and it is equally used by Santali healers (Bodding, 2011; Carrin-Bouez 1979, 1991). The founder of the indigenous knowledge transmitted among various Ojhā lineages is said to be the legendary Kamru Guru (Bodding 2011; Carrin-Bouez, 1991), possibly a preceptor from Kamrup (Assam) or one who has learnt traditional medicine, magic and witchcraft from Kamrup. The Ojhās' curative practices and techniques show sophisticated intermingling of Yogic medicine, herbal medicine based on the collection of particular leaves, roots, barks etc. and Fakiri medicine based on bodily substances and application of forced breath for curative purposes. Becoming an Ojhā implies a personal choice and a long training under a respected Guru: people from all social groups are virtually eligible to become Ojhās, although these professional healers and exorcists are usually members of Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (so called Hinduised aboriginal groups, e.g. Bagdi, Majhi, Lohar, etc.). Ojhās are not normally allowed to ask for any remuneration whatsoever for their healing sessions, although they can accept spontaneous offers of money or rice from the patient. Their main source of livelihood is usually different from their medical and shamanic activities which normally is that of daily agricultural labourer. The performer's activities as drummers, minstrels of Manasā songs and snake-charmers are confined to the ritual occasions and the festive periods related to the snake-goddess. After the monsoon season, at the end of the ritual period, the snakes which had been previously collected and kept in the woven baskets (Jhāmpi) are released into the wild. Apart from curing humans as well as cattle from snake-bites, and from any poisonous insect and reptile in general, Ojhās are specialised in healing from a number of disturbances, illnesses and disorders, such as sāper bātās, the "snake wind". It is believed that the snakes can exhale poison through their breath and this, carried by the wind, can affect a person showing specific symptoms. Ojhās are also called to cure patients suffering from possession by evil spirits, ghosts and witches (bātās lāgā, bhut dharā, dāini dharā), and from the evil eye (najar), and also from several similar circumstances¹⁰.

The Ojhās of Bengal are low-caste practitioners specialised in the healing of snake-bites and in the making of antidotes to cure poisonous snake-bites. For economical sustenance, they often perform

snake-charming, an appreciated entertainment in rural areas as well as the practices which are unavoidable during particular religious rituals and festivals. With the diffusion of western medicines even in remote rural areas and the governmental support of western medicine and western education, the indigenous knowledge of the Ojhās is seriously compromised and leads to rapid decline. The Ojhās' specialisations are equally challenged by the institutions, the religious establishment, and by left-wing activism. The performativity as well as healing competencies of the Ojhās are not recognised by the State whereas other groups of performers/practitioners are protected by the governmental recognition and the economic facilities granted with the “Folk Artist Identity Card”. Their heterodox shamanic practices are ostracized by both Hindu and Islamic religious establishments. Attacked as irrational superstitions, their healing techniques are strongly opposed by social activists and socialist theatre groups operating at the village level.

The treatment process: Before exploring some literary examples let's get some information about the treatment process of the snake bite. For successful activation of the charms it is necessary to know the proper application of the charm cure process, says the Gunins or the snake charmers.

- a) The messengers, who first come to call any Gunin to cure any snake bite patient, receive three charm-slaps on his breast. It is the first reaction of any Ojhā or Gunin. With this reaction he recites a charm (Mantra). From Sundarban area one such charm is collected by Dr. Subhas Mistri in a mixed language of Oriya and Bengali. He has quoted it in his book ‘DakkhiNbaNger Lokosamaaje Mantra’.

Chapar Saar: snake bite charm:

ওঁ খণ্ডে হাচুনী মুণ্ডে দা ক্যানে কু গুল

পত্রে শুনিলাম মা - মো যাইয়ে করবো কিশো

মারি চাপড় নাহি বিষ ওঁ।¹¹

[Om KhanDe HaanchunI MunDe daa

Kyane ku gul

Patre Shunilaam Maa

mo jaiye korbo kiSho

Maari chaapar naahi bish om.]

Meaning: Whenever it happened and the news delivered to me by the informer it was struck in my head. This news is not wrong. O Holy Mother! Till the time, I can reach to the patient; I am slapping the informer as prevention that the poison can be removed from the victim's body with your kindness.

After reciting this charm the Gunin slap for the third time to the messenger and then tie a knot in his own cloth to stop the spreading of the poison. He hit the knot with a mouth-breath and exuded his power that he can start his healing process from a distance.

- b) Then he examines the patient in a sitting position by 'jhaṛān' or beating by a chamar (fly whisk) or branches of Neem tree or Dhakai Henna and reciting charms.
- c) The way of moving the Chamar or Neem branch or Henna branch is from head to feet
- d) Then the Ojhā or Gunin apply the medicine made of some selected medicinal plant to the patient. They make a paste of medicinal herbs mixed with curd or milk or clarified butter/ghee or mirage or lemon etc. and form it as a tablet. Gunins prescribe these tablets to their patients. Sometimes they prepare magic armlet or amulet with the juices of various medicinal herbs.
- e) Gunin extract the poison by using three processes,
Firstly by using charms.
Secondly by sipping with the mouth.
Thirdly to call upon the biting snake by enchanting Kaṛi (cowrie), baggy fruit etc.
The belief is that these enchanted Kaṛi (cowrie), baggy etc. attract the biting snake towards the patient and it returned back and cure the patient by withdrawing the poison from the biting area of the patient's body.
- d) Assuming the affected area by moving hand or plate the Gunin prescribe the method of remedy either by *pucchan*, *jhāṛan*, *jhāmpān*, *chāpān* etc.
- e) To protect the patient from evil power sometimes they prescribe amulet, charm trinket, talisman etc.

f) At the time of binding the amulets the Gunin cover it with dust or rope and utter a mantra or spell.

g) He also examines the biting area if there is any remaining part of the tooth of the snake, if he found so; he cleans the area by moving the thread or long hair from upside to downside.

h) By squeezing the *gamocha* (body cleaning cloth) Ojhā can clean out the poison from the patient's body and by firing anything with uttering charms Ojhā can burn out the poison.

i) Ojhā or Gunin restrict his own sexual instinct and also the sexual instinct of the family members of the patient and stop the productivity of the home, and surroundings.

j) Ojhā or Gunin not only cure the patient but also divested the ability to harm of the poisonous snakes.

Charm and the charmer: From ancient days men are trying to imitate the natural sounds of bird, and other animals and imitate the natural sounds to improve their own power. With some beliefs the charms are used to manage evil power and also to enhance benevolent power. The charms are not anything special than a kind of songs. The spells are mainly hymns; created by the local Gunin or Ojhā or priest for enriching both the malevolent and benevolent power. These spells are recited by the priests with natural tune and the charms are formed with its natural power of effectiveness. Therefore the actual meaning of the word 'charm' is 'song'. The Ojhās and Gunins are efficient singer of their charms and their magical power is enabled to their patients or followers with the use of the charms. In the same way the term 'incantation' is also applicable as a kind of 'Geet' or music.

The charmer used to recite 'Stotra' at the time of holding amulets, armour or the tree roots or charmed ring; When they put some medicinal plants or charmed thing into the amulets the charmer or priests or Gunins recite both the 'Stotra' and the 'charm'. When the Gunins used to do any magic gesture they generally use gaze tactics or knock with many of their wonders. With these gestures they usually arrange some sacrifice, oblation of fire etc.

Use of Charm at the time of 'Gantuli' or tiding a knot at the spot of snake-bite:

'Gantuli' is type of amulet. To prevent of spreading the poison after snake bite, the Gunin tide a knot with a rope or cotton cloth binding the area of the biting. It helps him to treat the patient. There are some measures they take,

- Stop to spread the poison in the other parts of the body
- Charms can burn out the poison
- If necessary they sip the poison from the body

This *Gantuli* can protect the patient from evil eye also. When the Gunin or Ojhā put the medicine inside of the amulets to bind at the place of *Gantuli*, they recite this charm,

শব্দ শুনেছি আমি অমুক জনে কেটেছে সাপে।
এমন সময় নারদ মুনি জিজ্ঞাসা করে তাহার।

ওই শব্দে দেবগণ আহা আহা করে।
নারদ বলে কি হইয়াছে মহাদেব রাজার

জিজ্ঞাসা করি তোমায়। মহাদেব বলে – নারদ
পদ্মা কি করিলে, কতকগুলি নাগ রেখে
পদ্মা বলে লজ্জা দিও না, আমি এই
৬৪ দেবগণ সাক্ষী থাক তুমি।
উপরে না ধায় বিষ নীচে না ওলে।
থাকবে এ স্থলে।
আমার এই গাঁটুলি যদি লঙঘন হয় -
খসে ভূমে নেবে যায়। কার আজ্ঞা

পদ্মযোনি বাঁচিলে পদ্মযোনির জ্বালায়।
বাকি ছেড়ে দিলে তারে।
অঞ্চল মুখে দিলাম। এই অঞ্চলে
এই গাঁটুলি বাঁকি গির দিলাম আমি।
আমার এই গাঁটুলি না খুলি অমনিভাবে

চাঁদ সূর্যের মুখে কালি পড়ে শিবের জটা
শিব শিব শিব দোহাই তোমার।¹²

[*Shabda Shunechi aami omuk jane keteche saape. Eman samay Naarad muni jiggaasaa kare taahaar. raajaar*

Oi shabde debgan aaha aaha kare. Naarad bole ki haiyaache Mahaadeb

Jiggaasaa kari tomaay. Mahaadeb bale – Naarad Padmaa ki karile, katakguli Naag rekhe Padmaa bole lajjaa dio naa, aami ei 64 debgan saakkhi thaako tumi. Upare naa dhaay bish nIche naa ole. Thaakbe e sthale.

Padmajoni baanchile padmajoni jwaalaay. Baaki cheRe dile taare.

Anchal mukhe dilaam. Ei anchale Ei gaantuli baandhi gir dilaam aami.

Aamaar ei gaantuli naa khuli omnibhaabe

Aamaar ei gaantuli jadi langhan hay - Khase bhume nebe jay. Kaar aagna

Chaand surjer mukhe kaali paRe Shiber jataa Shib Shib Shib dohai tomaar.]

Meaning: Hearing sound of snake bite to Supreme God Mahadev, the gods and goddesses felt very anxious and Naarad, the divine informer, asked the God what happened to him. He told to ask goddess Manasā or Padmā to rescue or relief him from the severe irritation of snake bite. Then Padmā gave binding beside the wound to protect him and arrest the blood circulation from flowing towards his head. She did it with the witness of 64 gods and goddesses and claimed that the binding she made with the piece of her cloth that will not loose and the poison cannot flow upside or down. If this binding would not work then there will be black spot on Sun or Moon and the clotted hair of Lord Shiva will cut down to the ground. She requested Lord Shiva to please allow her to do this.

The charms are used in four ways;

1. In a loud voice
2. In a very low peached voice
3. Murmuring or without sound by only moving lips.
4. By mixing up and using the three methods

In our literature we can get three ways of using the charms, as;

- a. Narrative song, b. song, c. the text.

- a. Narrative Song: Snake Bite charm: Flower picking and collecting by Rahischandra (Harishchandra ?)

স্নান করি ডালা ধরি রহিসচন্দ্র রায় পুষ্প তুলিবারে শিশু যাত্রা করি যায়।।
খনেক দাঁড়ায় রহিস খনেক দৌড়ায় খনেতে ফিরিয়া চায়। খনেক কাতর খনেক ফাঁপড়
খনেক হাস্যমুখ
খনেক রঙ্গ খনেক ভঙ্গ খনেক পায় দুঃখ।।

.....
দৈব নিবন্ধ সেথা দারুণ বিধাতা। ব্রহ্মশাপে রহিস দাশ হইল সর্পাঘাতা।।
বুকেতে কামড় মারে দারুণ ফণি। ঘর্ম ছোটে ধরণী লোটে পড়িল ধরণী।।

.....
রাজার মহিষী হয়ে পরের দাসী হলেম। দুঃখীর ধন পুত্র তাও হারা হলেম।
মা বলিতে কেহ মোর নেই বড় মনস্তাপ। মরা পুত্র লয়ে কোলে অনলে দিব বাঁপ।।
মরাপুত্র কোলে নদের কূলে কান্দে উভরায়। ঘাটের ঘাটোয়ারি হাঁকে, জমার কড়ি চায়।।
আহা প্রভু হরিশচন্দ্র কোথায় রহিলেন, তোমার রোহিনী কোলে করি কান্দি অভাগিনী।

.....
দুড় দুড় করে অগ্নি উড়িল গগন।। ধরে মায়া অগ্নিবেড়ে -না মরিবে পুত্র তোর
হইল দৈববাণী।।

ধর্ম হইল বিরাজমানী, অমৃত নয়নে চান নির্বিষ হইল জীবন।।
জীবন পাইল চক্ষু মেলি চাইল পদ্ব হস্ত বুলাইল গায়। হাড়মাস রক্ত হতে বিষ ঘা মুখেতে
আয়।।

ঘা মুখেতে আসতে বিষ যদি করিস রা। ধর্মের আজ্ঞায় বিষ অমুকের অঙ্গে ভস্ম হয়ে
যায়।।

নেই বিষ নেই বিষ নেই বিষ মা মনসার আজ্ঞায়। নেই বিষ আস্তিকমুনি বিষহরির
আজ্ঞায়।¹³

[*Snaan kari daalaa dhari Rahischandra Ray Pushpo tulibare Shishu yatra kari jay
Khanik daaraay Rahis khanek douroy khanate firiyaa chay. Kanek kaatar khanek faapaR
khanek hasyamukh.*

Khanek ranga khanek bhanga khanek pay dukkha.

.....
*Daibo nibandho setha darun bidhata. Brahma shaape rahis das hailo sarpa ghaataa.
Bukete kaamoR maare daarun faNi. gharma chote dharaNI lote paRilo dharaNI.*

.....
*Raajaar mahishi hoye parer dasI holem. Duhkkhir dhan putra tao haaraa holem.
Maa bolite keho mor nei baRo mostap. Maraa putra loye kole anale dibo jhnaap.*

*Maraa putro kole nader kule kaande uvaray. Gaater ghaatoyari hake, jamaar koRi
chaay.
Aahaa pravu Harishchandra kothaay rahilen, tomaar Rohini kole kori kaandi avaagini
.....
DuR duR kore agni uRilo gagon. Dhare maayaa agni beRe – ‘naa moribe putra tor’
hailo daibobanI.
Dharma hailo birajmaani, amrito nayane chaan nirrbish hoilo jiban.
Jiban paailo chaokkhu meli caailo Padma astra bulaailo gay. HaaR maas rakto hote
biSh ghaa mukhete aay.
Ghaa mukhete aaste biSh jadi koris raa. dharmar aagnay biSh amuker ange malin hoye
jaa.
Nei biSh nei biSh nei bish maa manasaar aagnaay. Nei biSh aastik muni BiShaharir
aagnaay.]*

Meaning: This tale is taken from a Bengali narration ‘Harishchandra-Shaibya’ by local narrator.

In 19th century Sri Khitindranath Thakur wrote a book on this Puran story and it was much known and popular narration regularly acted in different local drama and Yatra. It was popular narration of Krittibasa’s Ramayana among Bengali people. Harishchandra was the ideal king and ideal human being, who sacrificed his kingdom, wealth, wife, son and even his own life for sake of his people. His son Rohish Das (Rohitashwa?) died by snake bite and his wife Rohini (Shaibya?) is weeping with the dead body. She has no idea where is his husband. When the body is surrendered to the Dom people for the last funeral, the Ojha tried for last chance to take him back to life. His magic chant is applied here and it is acted by him with full magical gestures and charms are applied to withdraw the poison from the body of the victim.

At the time of reciting this charm the Gunin brush the body with a branch of Neem tree from head to feet of the patient.

When a snake bitten patient is brought to a Gunin he began his treatment by worshipping the snake goddess Manasa. The charm of this worship is a song or worshipping song of Mother Goddess Manasa. At the special situation this song is called as ‘Smaranika’ or recalling song.

ওমা ধর্মযোগ আবাহনী (ধুয়া) ৩৩ কোটি দেবগণ
ভাসুকতে সবার গমন গো।
জয় মা জয় মন্ত্রকারিণী গো।।

লক্ষ্মীনারায়ণ নাম ধরি লক্ষ্মী যারে সেবেন চরণ।।
জয় মন্ত্রকারিণী আপনি গো মন্ত্র স্মরণে বিষ হইল পানি গো।।¹⁴

[O maa dharmajog aabaahanI (dhua) 33koti debgaN
vasukaate sabaar gaman go.
Jay maa jay mantrakaariNI go..

.....
LakshminaaraayaN naam dhaari Lakshmi jaare seben charaN.
Jay mantrakaariNI aapni go mantra smaraNe biSh haila paani go..]

Meaning: Praying to Mother Goddess and calling her in the name of Dharma and with the help of 33 million of gods and goddesses. She will definitely bless her son being pleased by the chanting, Jay Mother.

Name Lord Narayana and Goddesses Lakshmi also and praying to them too. They will heal the victim by their blessings and the poison will be changed to water by pleasing them with charms and getting their blessings.

The another form of spell or charm is reciting a text, i.e. beating the patient by spelling a harsh text to take him/her out of the gloominess or senseless condition. That is called as ‘Sannipaat JhaRan’;

ওগো মা হাড়ির ঝি। অমুকির কর্ণমূলে কার্ণিপাত বাড়াইয়ে করি পানি।

.....
মর শান্নিপাত টেনে নে মর বাড়নে মর। ফুকারে ফুকরে শান্নিপাত ফুকেতে মর।
কার আঙে – মা কালীর আঙে শিঘ্রকরি অমুকের কর্ণমূল শান্নিপাত ভস্ম হয়ে যা শিঘ্র
শিঘ্র শিঘ্র। ফুঁ।।¹⁵

[Ogo maa harir jhi. Amukir karNamUle kaarnipaat jhaRaiye kari paani.

.....
Mar Shaannipaat tene ne mar jhaaRane mar. Fukaare Fukare Shaanipaat fukete mar.
Kaar aagne – maa kaalir aagne Shigrakari amuker karNamul Shannipaat bhasma hoye
ja Shighra Shighra Shighra. Fu..... ..]

Meaning: By beating and burning, wishing it that all the evil powers may be removed by the blessings of Eternal Mother Goddess. Blowing breath and wishing the fulfilment

At the time of application of this charm the Gunin strike the patient by **bumble** a branch of ‘Dhakai Henna’ or Henna branch.

To cure the patient from enchantment of ghost they torture the patient by beating with branches of banana tree, intermit with mustered oil lamp, burn by hot oil thread etc. At that time the assistant of Gunin make a loud sound by beating drum or clapping hand and sway with the rhythm of the chant.

Except those type of charms the Pir or Gunin cure the patient by pouring holy water on the patient or pour the charmed holy water inside their mouth. When they prepare the water they recite charm at their own mind and people can see their lips are moving and they blow their breath on the water or on the patient. This treatment is called *Jal paraa*.

The Gunins learn these charms from their *Pir Gurus*. They try to satisfy all the Gurus, Gods and Goddesses as they bless them and keep the peace by withdrawing all the evils.

The charms are not only some unintelligible words, through the charm we can here many tales, fairy tales, creation myths, mysteries etc. These charms are generally long enough. The Gunin sing these charms with tune, rhythm, musical instrument. As a charm they recite or sing some parts from our epic like, Ramayan, Mahabharata, Bhagabat Gita, Mangal Kabya etc.

When they sing the 'Manthan Mantra' of snake bite after the worshipping chant, they strike from head to feet of the patient with the branches of Neem or Henna and try to sing the charm three to four times to take away the poison from the body.

মন্হনে মাতিল গোঁসাই কিবা কবে কথা। মন্হনে উপাজিল বিষ হস্তি মামুড় মাথা।।
সেই বিষ মহাপুরুষ খায় এক থাল। বুক বেয়ে পড়ে তার গোটা গোটা নাল।।
.....

এই অষ্টনাগ নিয়ে পদ্মরাণী জিয়াইতে গেলো। নাই বিষ নাই বিষ বলে বুকতে চাপড়
মারিল।।

নিঃশ্বাস ছাড়িয়া হর পাশমোড়া দিল। রাম রাম বলে ভক্ত উঠিয়া বসিল।।

শিঙ্গাতে ডম্বুর গান গাইতে লাগিল - নমঃ শিবায় নমঃ (৩ বার)।।¹⁶

[*Manthane maatila gnosaai kibaa kabe katha. Manthane Upaajila biSh hasti maamuR maathaa..*

Sei biSh mahaapuruSh khay ek thal. Buk beye paRe tar goTaa goTaa naal..
.....

Ei aShtonaag niye padmaraaNi jiyaaite gelo.. Naai biSh naai biSh bole bukete chaapaR maarila..

NihSwaas chaaRiyaa har paaShmoRaa dilo. Raam Raam bale vakta uthiyaa basila..

Shingaate Dambur gaan gaaita laagila - namah Shibaya namah (tin baar)..]

Meaning: After the great grinding of Mount Mainak by Vasuki Nag once poison arose and Lord Shiva drunk the entire poison. The thick drops of salaiva began to drop down by his chest.

These kind of long charms are taken from Puran or based on various mythological characters examples of the basic knowledge of the Gunin or Ojhā. They not only use the charm of controlling the snake poison, but also prevent the spreading by slapping the messenger and the religious devotee (victim) get well. All devotees began to worship Lord Shiva.

We can mention the mythological charms from Sanskrit Veda or Puranas and also from local myth of the folk gods and goddess, Guru- Gonsai characters or honourable personalities. Persona based charms are very rare, but used to cure long term process of Jhāmpān.

The Gunin or local doctor try to cure their patient by application of the charm one by one following the basic method – *Brahbhasār, Chutkisār, Cāpaṛ, Smaraṇ, Tāgā, Bāṅsār, Manthan* etc. and lastly the longest charms are applied as *Jhāmpān*. *Gunin* use these charms as a surgeon, who use surgical instrument to elicit desired effects during a surgery.

The *mantra* or charms are made of not only in Bengali language, but also these are mixed with Samskrit, Bengali, Oriya, Hindi etc. The Ojhā uses these charms as per his own knowledge and there is no such rule that every Gunin or Ojhā use the same charm for the same symptom.

Many such charms has been collected which are generally used to cure at last stage of a snake-bite patient highly vulgar in nature, indicating sexual excitement or sensation. Use of the words indicating penis, vajaina, intercourse etc. are generally granted as sensitive words and therefore when Ojhās utter the charm using these type of words or activity, none is allowed (especially children) to hear those charms or stay at the spot. This kind of Charm is generally recited or sung by sitting side by side to the patient to revive him/her from the coma condition, stimulate the nerves and energize the brain with sexual excitement. They recite the charms in high pitch noise with clapping and dancing. These charms are called ‘*Sār Mantra*’ or ‘*Jhāmpān Mantra*’. If the patient feels better to hear these exciting charms then the Gunin can be able to feed him/her some medicine through mouth. These charms are very near to folk sentiment and psychology and very simple to understand.

Jhāmpān:

হেদেরে বিঘেতে বড়া
শুনিল ধোপার ঝি
কেন বা গালি দেহ মোর।
বিশ্বের বড় জ্বালা

ভাঙব তোর দাঁতের গোড়া
তোরে আর বলিবা কি
ঠাপের বড় জ্বালা
বিঘেতে কাতর মানুষ হইল মরা।

আইল মনসা দিয়ে খায় বর
লক্ষ্মিন্দর মরেছে তার বিষ আসে
ঠাপের চোটে বিষ ধুতরা হয়
বিষহরীর স্বরণ বিষ ভস্ম হয়ে আয়
রক্তের সাগরে বিষ হাড়ে করে ভর।
নারী লোক যত হাসে তত বিষ খসে।
ধুতরা হইয়ে বিষ হইল ক্ষয়।
নেই বিষ, নেই বিষ মা মনসার আজ্ঞায়।¹⁷

In these charms one special feature is remarkable, ‘*Aggnā Smaraṇ*’ or ‘Offering *Dohai*’; i.e. thanks giving to the Guru or Teacher and to the God/Allah. Another remarkable feature is no mention of any special religious god/guru/pir/etc. Most of the charms are secular in nature. Some of the charms are made for only one religious Guru or Gods and Goddesses. Those are ‘*Ek HeRe*’ or made for one religious sect only. These Charms are divided by Hindu and Muslim Gunins. Another part is called ‘*Du HeRe*’ or made for more than one Religious Guru/ Peer/ Gods-Goddesses.

The charms are used for three purposes;

1. For self-prevention
2. To cure from any disease
3. For Evil-eye purposes

Therefore these folk or local charms used by local Gunin or Ojhā are the oral heritage of the indigenous people of India. I have collected these charms from South Bengal but this type of various charms can be found in every state of India. These charms are more ancient than Vedic civilization and its cultural discourse. In the later period both the cultures mixed up with each other and we can find and categorize the influences within these charms. These charms are prepared in local languages and the Gunins preserve their charm as written documents. Gunins and Ojhās have their note book with various noted charms. Therefore these are not only oral literature; but also consist of written documents and have the archival value. Vedic charms are very clear to understand but the local charms have some hidden meaning and not always very clear to understand. Like Vedic chants the local charms are also written or created both as poem and prose. Vedic charms have no relation with general life but the local charms are made by the people of the people and for the people. Vedic charms are classic, methodical and bookish; but the local charms are very much related to ‘Tantra’.

In Bengal the charms of curing snake-bite patient can be found in the literature also. In Charyapad of 10th century AD we can found many examples of such charms; like,

তাংকুরুকুল্লারপকরিত্রহগ্র।
অহনিসিবীঅহন্তেদেহগ্র।।
গুরুবঘনেদিড়করিমাণছ

ওণঅসবরপাবিসরাকরেহাণ্।।¹⁸

[*Taang kurukullahrup kari trhagra.*
ahanisi bia hante dehaagra..
gurubaghane diRha kari maaNahu
ONa Sabarpaa bisaraa kare haaNahu..]

Meaning – You come forward as Kurukulla. Day and night serve to produce useful material from the seed. Obey the words of your teacher. Teacher Sabarpa ask you to take out the poison by beating a hard slap. [Sen, 1966]

There are so many *charyas* or slokas was sung and written as *Sahazjan* which can be traced from the Buddhist religious and philosophical manuscript and the same culture is practiced till now by the *Peer/ Poigambar, Gunin, Ojhā, Baul/ Faqir* and the same type of sects and these can be traced in writing and reciting charms by the *Neoyaries* and *Brajacharyas*.

In Bengali various kinds of charms we can found in Mangalkavya and other lores, ballads, musical poems etc. I am quoting a stanza from the epic Mahabharata in Roman letters,

“ *Sangmantrya mantriviScaiba sa tathā mantratwatwabit.*
Prāsādang kārāmās ekastamvang surakkhitam..
Rakkhānca bidadhe tatra viShajaSouShdhāni cha.
Brahmanām MantrasiddhāngScha sarbato bai nyazojayat..

[Mahabharat/Adi/37/29-30]

Here Parikshit has been bitten by a tick by taking shape of a snake, PuNye. In Manasā Mangal Kavya the Kālñāginī sent by Manasā to cut the hero Lakshmindar. Though the modern scientific knowledge has proven, that both the PuNye and the Kālñāginī are not poisonous.

The general belief is that to cure a snake bitten patient it needs 64 charmed story or *Kahan* to tale. (64 Kahan = 81,920). It is said that Behulā revived her dead snake bitten husband in a new life by applying the 64 *Kahan* of magic charm. Till now the Ojhās and Gunins are following those charms. To get a relief from an acute case the reliable Ojhā apply those charms at South Bengal. Though, we are losing our ancient knowledge system rapidly. At present it is rare to find out the genuine Gunin, who has preserved his traditional charms to use. In later period, the 64 Kahan or story or charmed song reduced by 64 lines of a charm and then after it reduced to utter 64 words only, and then it became standardized as a special charm of 64 words.

Ojhās are known as ‘Shamans’ of the western witchcraft. Their profession is ancient and in every ancient civilization we can find this profession as an ancient culture or belief of the pre-historic people, who are called indigenous people of that specific land. From pre-historic period the Shaman- Gunins are depended upon the mother-nature. They cure their patients with the help of various Ayurvedic medicinal herbs for application at the wound and for taking it inside the body in paste/liquid form. They try to keep the patient awake and energised by continuous reciting or singing various types of charms.

There are three types of work practiced by the Ojhā.

- a. Treatment of a snake-bite patient
- b. Hypnotising of mesmerising the snake
- c. Collection of snakes, calling them to rescue or capturing for business purpose.

As per their division of work the snake catchers are called 'Bāidyā' or 'bede' in Bengali. Their profession is to catch and collect the live snakes and sell snakes, its skin, poison, meat, etc and earn money. Sometimes they showcase various snakes in front of public, play 'bin' or specific trumped made for snake charming. The Iluras of South India are this type of snake charmer or snake /rat/rabbit catchers. They are tribal group like Mar from Rajasthan, Patiā-Das of Odisha, Chakmā of north-east India, Pāliyerā of south-western part of India etc. paundra-Austroloid group of people of Extended Bengal, all are tribal *Sāpure/ Sāprā/bede/bediyā/bāidyā/ bajikar* etc. This Bedia groups are vagabond and lead a very uncertain life. They mainly catch snakes and rat and lock them inside an earthen pot. We can see the same things to be practiced by the Irulas also.

They both are tribes of India. Therefore their culture is same. Both of these tribes and all the other snake catcher or snake charmer tribal people are fighting for their existence. They all collect poison from the poisonous snakes and sell it to the medicinal stake holders. In the present day also, these snake charmers call the snake back to the bitten man through their charm and let the snake bite again the patient to cure him/her. These charms are called in Bengali 'āhbwan mantra' or 'calling charm' and like this, they can return back the snake from human. This kind of charm is called in Bengali as 'Chālān mantra' or 'backward charm'.

Among the Ojhā or Sāpure only some are able to make their own disciples through *Gurumukhi Bidya* or Oral transmission of knowledge. Except very reliable and near one they do not baptize any random student or assistant. Among Irulas we do not see any such tradition but among Sāpure community there are such traditions. Worship of the live snake is found among the Totem-fertilizing religious sects. In South India *Devadasis* worship snake by keeping the snakes as pet. The 'Teel' community of Maharashtra worship live Mayal snake. In Bengal people worship Mother Goddess 'Manasa' in the auspicious day of *Nag Panchami* and *Dashahara*. Months of May and June being summer season and very hot and month of July being monsoon season at the eastern India and in Bengal people face snake bite very often in the forest and river bank areas especially. Therefore they worship the snake god in this time. The priest worships a platform under the peepal tree or the *Manasa/ Seez plant* -a kind of cactus by offering milk and banana in the day of *Nag Panchami* and also worship Vastu serpent on the auspicious day of *Poush Samkranti* or winter solstice. From the ancient time of Sindhu civilization people worship Peepal tree or Aswattha tree (Wild-spread tree) as fertility god by offering the handmade snake model. As it seems that the Wild-spread is tree womb and the serpent is a symbol of a man. In every civilization serpents and snakes represent fertility or a creative life force; they are symbol of rebirth also.

In South India also the Peepal Tree or Aswattha (Wild-spread tree), Snuhi or Mansasiz or a special type of Cactus are venerable trees. They symbolize the white thick juice of the cactus as human sperm and very effective anti-septic and lifesaving product. There the tribal people who are the nomad and hunter in profession take this as food and believe that this special fluid help to develop their power of fertility. The statue of serpent they worship are *Ashtanāg*, *Naba nāg*, *beyallis nāg* etc. As per their own traditional practice one particular family can worship their own specific statue of snake god.

The Manasā cult:

The Manasā cult is not local Bengali cult at all. In Brahmabaibarta Puran, there we have first met with Manasā or Jaratkaru as the sister of Vasuki. The name of the husband of the Goddess is also Jaratkaru. At the later stage we can find Manasā as the daughter of Shivā. By nature she is very angry, harsh and revengeful. She is depicted as duel nature of man and woman and created as the reverse character of Vasuki. In the 6.3.4 *sukta* or stanza of Panini's manuscript we can find the name of Manasā and her identity. The synonym of the Latin name 'Venus' is also Manasā. In the *vāsān pala* or immersion poem and in the vows of entire Bengal and the adjacent area we can found the name of Manasā. There are various taboos also practiced by the people of this area against the fear of the snake bite. In Dravidian culture also this same fear overwhelms them and the snake goddess Manchammā is worshipped to get relief from the fear. Manchammā is the origin of the name Manasā. In Mahisur and Karnatak her name is Mudāmā and Mone-Manchmmā, in Andhra Pradesh Nāgammā-Bālanāgammā, in Odisha she is Pātkumārī, Khingeshwarī, in Assam the Khasia people call her as Thelan. Everywhere she is mother goddess and derived from the matriarchical culture. Everywhere people believed in matriarchical culture before they got mixed up with the Aryan civilization. The original belief on Tantra and the power of charm, magic and the power of witchcraft was depicted in this matriarchical -culture, where mother goddess is the main power and she is equivalent to the nature. The power of nature was watched and studied and then it was assimilated with the characteristics mother goddesses of various places. They were considered as the main source of power. Later stage this hereditary practices and beliefs were followed by the male priests, Gunins and Ojhās. The source was inherited by the *sahaz jān* followers or the natural worshippers, who didn't follow or rather now also they do not follow any particular religion. They worship the inner soul of man, they are totally involved with their *sadhanā* or meditation.

We can find this cult among the Buddhists. They have the goddess as *Bishaharī* or Jangulik. In Hashacharit we can got to know that the *Sapure* tribe were known as 'Jāngulik'. In Atharba Veda the snake goddess is the daughter of a hunter and she is the same goddess as Vaidic Saraswati and Buddhist Jāngulī. In Bengal, Bihar and Orissa the same goddess is called Bishaharī Manasā. In Orissa the auspicious day *Nāg Panchamīs* is called as Jānguli Panchami. In Buddhist Bazrayan Devi Tārā can relieve from eight great fears. One of the fear is fear from snake bite. The tribe, Oraon of Ranchi district of Jharkhand believe in their ancient serpent goddess Manasā. Among

them the serpent Ojhā is called as 'Nāgmatī. They worship her in the month of May-June, July-August by sacrificing hens and cuckoos. The Ho tribes of Singbhum district worship goddess Manasā as a piled up soil.

It has been proved through research that the practice of worshipping the snake goddess was first appeared in the culture of south India. There were no proof found in the Vedic literature about worshipping of any snake goddess but in south India existence of the local folk goddess and the culture of Deva Dāsi dance are main proofs of existence of worshipping snake goddess, where in dance style we can see the movements like serpent and the mating position of snake as dance form. In the period 10th-12th century many people came from south to Bengal region as soldiers. They brought their culture and the goddess Manchammā. That goddess was transformed as goddess Manasā in Bengal. In 'Charyapad' literature of that period, the evidence of first Bengali poems, we can see that the lower caste people especially Dom, Shabar who were not treated as a part of civilized people or tribes who were enjoying their life outside the society as *Sahaziā Sadhak* and the women of those tribes were free to exercise their own beliefs and religious opinions. Among the Hepoi Indians of Arizona the women dance as snake for rain. In Kerala at the day of winter-solstice people enjoy the vow of Sarpa-kadu or Vasuki raised the Earth at his shoulder. This festival is watched in West Bengal also as Vastupuja. In the *sarpa-kāru* festival the lower caste virgin girls welcome the serpents by spreading red fine cloth on the ground. The design of ālpanā is like the mating snakes drawn with the mixture of rice powder, red colour and turmeric powder. They place four banana trees at the four sides (outside) of the ālpanā. There are so many examples all over India to prove sufficiently that the snake worship is within the ancient indigenous people's belief system. The form of worshipping is also ancient (pre-vedic) by using charms on the ground of magic realism.

Therefore serpent culture is a pre-historian tradition of human. Man not even fears the dangerous snakes but they obey their goodness of power. It's a mixed mesmerised feeling always felt by human about the serpent world. The Nāg world is not the hell but it is the other world where Nāgs are lived as fairies. Actually it is the low land, or deep forest area surrounded by the sea. The serpents or snakes are symbol of fertility cult. Therefore people worship them. All over the world we can find various symbols, rituals, festivals, beliefs and magic realism of the snake cult. In Greece, Iran, Babylon, North Pole area, Egypt and in many places snake cult was very much prominent in their sculpture, art, architecture, rituals and beliefs. In literature also we can get the idea. In the south and South East Asia, Africa, South America, Australia there are huge propaganda material in circulation about this cult and also about the fertility cult. The Ojhā cult is also seen everywhere and as a mother cult and nature worship this specific cure system has been identified. This magical power has a negative part also and that is evil eye witchcraft. Magic has both the power benevolent and malevolent. But with this charm based activities there is no connection of the snake hunting, collecting of poison, earning by selling the poison, snake skins and bones of the snakes, rats, and other animals. The people who earn their livelihood by these activities and by

showing circus by various trapeze games are tribal people. They don't know the magical charms of the Ojhā or Gunin. They earn their livelihood with their own ability and skill. Skilled power as they learnt from generation to generation is their main source of living. Therefore the tribal group named Ilura has not any connection with the belief system of the woman priest or Ojhā but Ojhā has the power of catching the snakes and uproot the poisonous teeth of snake. In all over the world the *Bede* or *Sāpure* types of tribes are called Gypsy. They have various names but they are of low caste hunter gatherer tribal people who are not connected or related with the Ojhās. In Assam Ojhā dance is very significant. It is also ritualistic dance form and related to energize the patient and cure them. With their charm song and dance all the evil powers go away, this is the belief¹⁹.

Conclusion: The *Sāpure* or *Irula* all are ethnic groups of India, who have separate cultures than the *Gunin* but all deal with snake. The culture of *Gunin* or *Ojhā* is to rescue or save the snake-bitten people or to do any black magic on any client. They make their disciple to continue their profession and tradition and protect and conserve their old manuscript etc. This discipline is owned by them and they try to left next generation(?). On the contrary the tribal people own their traditional knowledge which is passed on to generation after generation. From southern part of India we can collect a traditional knowledge about Nag or snake gods and goddesses, from tribes who have ethnic knowledge of snake hunting. It is proved that from South India the practice of snake worship had started. There we have got ancient song and drama on the snake gods and goddesses. The *Naga* caste is the first worshipper of snake. In both part of India this culture is now becoming obsolete. The tribes are threatened as criminal. The profession of the *Gunin* is now challenged before the developed scientific knowledge. Many allopathic medicine and cure system is now available to the general public. The unfortunate condition of the tribal community and the delicate and endangered status of their language (*māntā bhāṣā*) is alarming. It was found in a community rally in Kolkata in 2008. Simultaneously, it is acknowledged that a substantial no of people annually die of snake-bite in West Bengal, especially because of want of anti-venom. A little documentary on You Tube produced by ICS is available at the link <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Dup3Pj-mZXY>. Bedia snake-charmers during a protest organized in Kolkata in 2009 complained that Anti Venom Serum is (paradoxically) scarcely available in medical infrastructures. Hence their rightful requests were mainly for the activation of a licensing system and giving them permission to start snake farms. They proposed a collaborative system between schools, hospitals and indigenous people having knowledge about snake and snake bite. Awareness programs conducted at schools would contribute to inform common people about snake-related knowledge, and thus reduce the belief in superstition and the unnecessary slaughtering of innocuous snakes. At the same time, assisted by complementing modern medical practices, the local healers could collaborate with pharmacies, hospitals and clinics, and thus the number of casualties from snake-bites could be substantially reduced. The BFI also proposes to form "Rescue Teams" (Dash 2011: 94) that can be available for saving

endangered wildlife and dispelling fear of village households from poisonous snakes, which the Bedes know how to professionally catch and release into the right environment.

End Note:

¹Mistri, Subhas (2016)

²Bedias are already mentioned in colonial studies in the tribes of India and in early anthropological works. See Wise (1883), Williams (1912), Dalton (1978).

³Personal interview with Ojhās and Bedes

⁴Snake-catchers, who would generally receive about Rs.700 for selling the poison extracted from one snake.

⁵Performative and artistic activities by the Bede groups are: magic tricks, juggling, acrobatics, tattoo making, scroll-painting and storytelling, disguising with colourful masques and costumes (bahurūpī) etc.

⁶The text is available on the website of the Indian Ministry of Environment and Forests (envfor.nic.in/legis/wildlife/wildlife1c7.pdf 20/03/2016). Several communities whose survival is connected to the taming and use of wild animals have been jeopardized due to the enforcement of this law. About the impact of the Wildlife Preservation Act on the itinerant performer groups Hawadiga and Qalandar in Karnataka see Ajit Kumar (2012- 13).

⁷See official website at www.janasanskriti.com (14/04/2016)

⁸Jahan (2014: 508); Ghosh et al. (2014: 77).

⁹See also Jahan (508).

¹⁰See also Bhowmik (1978)

¹¹Mistri, Subhas. 2000

¹²⁻¹⁸ *ibid*

¹⁹Mistri, Subhas. 2016

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